

VISIONS OF MEANING FOR IMPACT-ORIENTED INFORMATION SYSTEMS RESEARCH IN TIMES OF POLYCRISIS: QUO VADIS?

Call for Contributions

14/06/2026 – 14:00 to 17:30, ECIS 2026 Ancillary Meeting, Milan, Italy

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Motivation

We are navigating an era of unprecedented global transformation, marked by interconnected ecological, social, economic, and political challenges—a “polycrisis” (e.g., Lawrence et al., 2024). This context creates both urgency and opportunity for Information Systems (IS) research explicitly oriented toward societal impact. However, at the very moment such research is most needed, the meaning of “impact” itself is contested and elusive.

Established debates about relevance versus rigour, the research-practice gap, and systematic research programmes have tended to reproduce Western-centric, techno-optimistic assumptions (Dwivedi et al., 2024; Applegate, 1999; Robey & Markus, 1998; Straub & Ang, 2011). Critical perspectives from systems thinking (e.g., Ison, 2008; Ulrich, 1994), philosophy of technology (e.g., Ihde, 1993), and emerging fields like responsible innovation (e.g., Smolka & Böschen, 2023) and transformative research (e.g., Horcea-Milcu et al., 2024), have received relatively little attention in the IS field, and their absence is increasingly difficult to justify. Meanwhile, the rapid rise of Generative Artificial Intelligence (GenAI) adds another dimension as it is reshaping what research questions we ask, how we conduct inquiry, and what kinds of impact we can plausibly claim.

This is, in short, a profound “moment of truth” for Impact-Oriented Information Systems (IIS) research. The central question we must ask is: “Quo Vadis?” – “Where are we going?”. This is not merely an academic inquiry, but rather a challenge that calls on each IIS researcher to reflect on their personal and our collective paths forward. Are our current theories, methodologies, and focal areas adequate for the scale and nature of the challenges we face? How can IIS research genuinely contribute to navigating a polycrisis and fostering sustainable and equitable futures? This workshop’s call for contributions invites IS researchers to step back and reflect on these questions.

A particular highlight of the workshop will be a distinguished panel featuring **Amber Young** (University of Arkansas, USA), **Carla Bonina** (University of Surrey, United Kingdom), **Markus Zimmer** (University of Agder, Norway), and **Andreas Nilsson** (Dimatech, Sweden). Contributors will therefore have the opportunity to place their ideas in dialogue with leading international perspectives from academia and practice.

What We Are Looking For

We invite short contributions of up to 6 pages that sit deliberately between a position statement and a piece of empirical or conceptual research. We are looking for well argued, reflective perspectives that are grounded in your experience or research but reach toward broader implications.

A strong contribution will engage with the guiding questions in the next section in the following way:

1. Articulate a clear, argued stance on what “impact” means in your research context (Q1);
2. Draw on concrete experiences, cases, or findings to substantiate that stance (Q2);
3. Engage critically with (at least one of) the other guiding questions below (Q3 - Q5); and
4. Open up questions or tensions rather than resolve them.

Contributions may draw on any research approach, including design science research, action research, engaged scholarship, policy-oriented research, or critical IS research.

Guiding Questions

You are not required to address all questions. Addressing three with genuine depth is preferable to a superficial treatment of all five. The questions are prompts, not a template.

Q1 — What does “impact” mean to you?

How do you understand impact in relation to your own research? When is your work meaningful — to whom, in what ways, and under what conditions? How has your understanding evolved, and what tensions or contradictions have you encountered?

Q2 — Impact in practice

Can you illustrate, through concrete experience, how you pursue impact in your work? What has worked, what has failed, and what have you learned? What structural, institutional, or epistemic conditions shape what is possible?

Q3 — Meaningful vs. impactful research

What research topics do you find personally meaningful? What topics do you believe are likely to be impactful in a broader societal sense? How much do these two sets overlap — and what does any gap between them reveal about our field?

Q4 — Researching in times of polycrisis

What does it mean to you to be a researcher today, amid interconnected crises? How does the polycrisis context shape your sense of responsibility, your choice of methods, your relationship with practice, or your understanding of what counts as valid knowledge?

Q5 — Generative AI and the future of impactful research

How is GenAI changing IIS research — not just as an object of study, but as a force shaping how research is conducted, evaluated, and communicated? Does GenAI expand or narrow the possibilities for societal impact? Does it introduce new ethical responsibilities for IIS researchers? What new questions does it open, and which established ones does it foreclose?

Submission Details

- **Format:** Short contribution of up to 6 pages (including references) in PDF format, following the [ECIS template](#) (similar to Debate and provocation proposals). The author details should already be included in the initial submission.
- **Tone:** Between a position statement and research, similar to a well-argued editorial or research commentary.
- **Key dates:**
 - o **Initial submission window:** From now until **May 15, 2026**.
 - o **Feedback on submissions:** On a rolling basis until **May 22, 2026**.
 - o **Deadline for final submissions:** **May 29, 2026**.
- **Submission:** The submission and review process is managed through a Zenodo community. An active Zenodo account is required. Simply upload your submission file with basic information to the following community: <https://zenodo.org/communities/iis-workshop/>. The other information fields in the upload form are optional.
- For further questions please feel free to reach out to iis-workshop@proton.me.

Review Process And Outcomes

The organizing team will provide feedback on all contributions ahead of the workshop. Our goal is to have a light-touch, constructive review process that will result in the selection of a diverse range of submissions to foster productive and constructive discussion during the workshop. All selected contributions will be assigned a Digital Object Identifier (DOI) and made publicly available as part of the workshop proceedings. They will also be distributed to participants before the workshop begins.

At the workshop, a combination of a panel discussion and more interactive group discussions will facilitate the exchange of ideas. Depending on the volume and quality of the submissions received, we may explore the possibility of holding a follow-up virtual event, creating a collective publication, or publishing a special issue in a journal.

Researchers whose submissions are not selected for publication remain welcome to attend the workshop and participate in the discussions.

Who Should Submit

This call is open to IS researchers at all career stages — from late-stage doctoral students to senior scholars — as well as to researchers from adjacent disciplines (e.g., science and technology studies, sustainability science, philosophy of technology, design research) and to reflective practitioners engaged with IIS research. Interdisciplinary and cross-institutional contributions are especially welcome.

This is the 1st Impact-oriented Information Systems Workshop workshop. We plan to hold it on multiple occasions and hope to build a growing community within the AIS.

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